

EVALUATION OF THE PROTECTIVE ACTIVITY OF A HYDRO-ETHANOLIC EXTRACT OF THE TRUNK BARK OF *TERMINALIA SUPERBA* ENGL. AND DIELS (COMBRETACEAE) ON NEPHROTOXICITY INDUCED BY GENTAMICIN IN RATS

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: The kidney is attacked and affected by insufficiency. Many people suffer from kidney failure. Given the difficulties of treatment with conventional medicine, the WHO has prescribed traditional medicine for support. **Objective:** This aims to help populations benefit from natural care by evaluating the protective effect of *Terminalia superba* extract in rats made nephrotoxic by gentamicin. **Methods:** 36 Wistar rats divided into 6 groups of 6 rats each were used. Batches I and II received distilled water orally at 1 mL/100 g bw for 12 days and from the 5th day, batch II received gentamicin by intraperitoneal injection at 150 mg/kg bw. Batches III to V were treated orally with *Terminalia superba* extract (125; 250 and 500 mg/kg bw) for 12 days. From the 5th, gentamicin was injected into them. On the 13th day, blood was collected and serum used to measure certain markers of kidney damage, some electrolytes and the relative weight of the kidneys was determined. **Results:** Gentamicin induced significant increases in urea, creatinine, sodium, chlorine, relative kidney weight and significant decreases in potassium levels in rats compared to the control group treated with distilled water. In animals pretreated with *Terminalia superba*, the levels of urea, creatinine, sodium, chlorine, and the relative weight of the kidneys decreased significantly while the potassium level underwent partial increases. **Conclusion:** *Terminalia superba* extract has a protective effect on the kidneys due to its ability to regulate the levels of renal serum markers (urea, creatinine) increased in the presence of gentamicin.

KEYWORDS: *Terminalia superba*, protective, kidneys, gentamicin, rat.

INTRODUCTION

The kidney is an organ that maintains the hydro-electrolyte balance of the body by varying the quantity of water and different plasma constituents through their elimination or retention in the production of urine. Its role is essential, not only, in the elimination of end products of metabolism and foreign substances such as urea, uric acid, drug metabolites and toxins, but also in retaining essential substances such as glucose, amino acids and minerals.^[1] However, the kidney's functioning is commonly attacked by some of these metabolites. This is the basis of known kidney dysfunctions. Faced with the difficulties of care and the increasing number of kidney damage, the WHO recommends that developing countries study medicinal plants in order to establish

their healthy therapeutic use by the population.^[2] In order to contribute to the achievement of this goal, this study was undertaken to evaluate the preventive effect of the hydro-ethanolic extract of the trunk bark of *Terminalia superba* in rats rendered nephrotoxic to gentamicin. Indeed, work already carried out in our laboratory with *Terminalia superba* has shown its anti-ulcer, anti-inflammatory and hepato-protective effects.

MATERIELS AND METHODS

Preparation of the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* (Ts)

The trunk bark of *Terminalia superba* was washed with distilled water, cut into small pieces and dried in an oven at 45 °C for 5 days. These small pieces were finely

pulverized with a RETSH brand electric grinder, type SM 100 (Haan, Germany). The extraction method used was that of^[3] during which 100 g of *Terminalia superba* trunk bark powder were macerated for 24 hours in one liter of a Water-Ethanol mixture (30/70 v/v). The resulting marc was put back into 0.5 L of this same mixture for 12 hours. The solutions obtained were mixed and filtered through hydrophilic cotton, then through Whatman 3 mm filter paper. The filtrates were evaporated and dried in a Friucell brand oven (Germany) at 55 °C for 24 hours. A brown powder which constitutes the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* (Ts) was thus obtained.

Experimental process

This study was conducted according to the approval of the Animal Ethics Committee of Nangui ABROGUA University, Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire. The method used for these tests is that described by^[4] with a slight modification. Thirty-six adult *Wistar* rats were used. These animals weighing between 100 and 160 g from the animal facility of the Laboratory of Physiology, Pharmacology and Pharmacopoeia (L3P) of Nangui ABROGUA University (Abidjan, Côte d'Ivoire) were

acclimatized to the experimental conditions for one week, then divided into 6 groups of 6 rats each. Rats in group 1 were orally administered distilled water at a rate of 1 mL per 100 g bw for 12 days. The rats in group 2 received orally distilled water at a rate of 1 mL per 100 g of body weight for 12 days and from the 5th day, they received gentamicin (Tongmei Laboratory, Togo) by intraperitoneal injection at a dose of 150 mg/kg bw. As for those in groups 3; 4 and 5 were respectively treated orally with the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* (Ts) at doses of 125; 250 and 500 mg/kg bw for 12 days. From the 5th day, these rats were treated with gentamicin intraperitoneally at a dose of 150 mg/kg bw. Finally, the rats in group 6 only received by gavage the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* (Ts) at a dose of 500 mg/kg bw, for 12 days. At the end of the study, blood was collected from the orbital vein of the eyes of the rats and the serum was used to determine the serum concentrations of certain markers of renal damage (creatinine, urea, total proteins) and some electrolytes (potassium, sodium and chlorine) using a spectrophotometer (HITACHI 902-Roche, Japan) using standard methods presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Biochemical parameters determined in serum.

Biochemical parameters	References
Creatinine	[5]
Urea	[6]
Total protein	[7]
Potassium	[8]
Sodium	[8]
Chlorine	[8]

Additionally, the relative kidney weights of the animals were determined using the following formula:

$$\text{Relative weight (\%)} = \frac{\text{Animal kidney weight}}{\text{Animal weight}} \times 100$$

Statistical analyzes

Statistical analysis of the data was carried out using GraphPad Prism 5.01 software (San Diego, California, USA). Results are expressed as means followed by the standard error of the mean (M ± SEM). The Dunnet test supplemented by the Tukey post-test for the comparison of all the means were used. The significance threshold is set at p < 0.05 for the expression of the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

Effects of *Terminalia superba* extract on gentamicin-induced nephrotoxicity

Effects of different treatments on serum creatinine level

The results in "Fig. 1" indicate the effects of gentamicin (150 mg/kg bw) and doses of hydro-ethanolic extract of

Terminalia superba (125, 250 and 500 mg/kg bw) on serum creatinine level. The creatinine level in the group of rats receiving gentamicin at 150 mg/kg bw increased significantly compared to the control group. This level is 0.90 ± 0.080 mg/dL for the group of control rats and 2.82 ± 0.43 mg/dL for the gentamicin batch. Ts causes a dose-dependent reduction in the effect of gentamicin on serum creatinine level. Indeed, the serum creatinine level of rats in groups pretreated with Ts doses of 250 and 500 mg/kg bw by gavage followed by gentamicin decreased significantly compared to the group of rats treated with gentamicin. The values are 1.22±0.15 mg/dL and 1.01±0.18 mg/dL, respectively. As for the rats treated only with the dose of 500 mg/kg bw of Ts, the increase in creatinine level of 0.97± 0.102 mg/dL is not significant compared to the control group.

Fig. 1: Effects of different treatments on creatinine level.

Values are presented as the mean \pm S.E.M. ($n = 6$). ### indicates $p < 0.001$ in comparison with the control group (Group I). *** indicates ($p < 0.001$) in comparison with the gentamicin-treated group (Group II). Ts: *Terminalia superba*; GM: gentamicin.

Effects of different treatments on serum urea level

The results of the effects of gentamicin and the doses of the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* on the urea level of the rats are presented in "Fig. 2". The urea level of the group of rats treated with gentamicin (150 mg/kg bw) significantly increased compared to the control group. Indeed, this level increased from 2.54 ± 0.153 g/dL in the control group to 4.14 ± 0.566 g/dL in the group having received gentamicin. Ts induces a dose-

dependent reduction in the increase caused by gentamicin in the serum urea level. The values obtained indicate a significant reduction in the group of rats treated with the dose of 500 mg/kg bw of *Terminalia superba*. Indeed, it is 2.82 ± 0.2 g/dL compared to 4.14 ± 0.566 g/dL in the group of rats which received gentamicin. The group of rats treated with only the dose of 500 mg/kg bw of Ts obtained a level of 2.62 ± 0.124 g/dL.

Fig. 2: Effects of different treatments on urea level.

Values are presented as the mean \pm S.E.M. ($n = 6$). ## indicates $P < 0.01$ in comparison with the control group (Group I). * Indicates ($p < 0.05$) comparison with the gentamicin-treated group (Group II). Ts: *Terminalia superba*; GM: gentamicin.

Effects of different treatments on serum total protein levels

The effects of gentamicin and doses of the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* on the serum total protein level of rats are presented in "Fig. 3". The total protein level of the group of rats receiving gentamicin at a dose of 150 mg/kg bw did not increase significantly compared to the control group. Indeed, the total protein level which was 5.47 ± 0.296 g/L for the

control group increased to 6.21 ± 0.0984 g/L for the group treated with gentamicin. Groups of batches pretreated with doses of 125, 250 and 500 mg/kg bw of Ts by gavage followed by gentamicin showed a non-significant decrease in total protein levels compared to the group receiving gentamicin only. They are respectively 5.84 ± 0.099 g/L, 5.72 ± 0.372 g/L and 5.62 ± 0.140 g/L. Thus, Ts causes a non-significant decrease in the increased effect on total protein levels induced by

gentamicin. The total protein level of the group of rats which received only the dose of 500 mg/kg bw also did not vary significantly.

Fig. 3: Effects of different treatments on total protein levels.

Values are presented as the mean \pm S.E.M. ($n = 6$). Ts: *Terminalia superba*; GM: gentamicin.

Effects of different treatments on serum electrolyte levels

Effects of different treatments on sodium levels

Fig. 4 presents the effects of gentamicin and doses of hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* on sodium levels. These results indicate a significant increase in the sodium level of the group of rats treated with gentamicin which is 102 ± 12.7 mmol/L compared to that of the control group having received distilled water which is 60.6 ± 8.01 mmol/L. Ts significantly reduced the gentamicin-induced increase in sodium levels. Indeed,

the groups of rats gavaged with doses of 250 and 500 mg/kg bw of Ts followed by intraperitoneal administration of gentamicin showed a significant decrease in the level of this electrolyte. These values are respectively 63.7 ± 2.08 mmol/L and 58.9 ± 3.86 mmol/L. As for rats gavaged with only the dose of 500 mg/kg bw of Ts, the level is 70.5 ± 3.34 mmol/L. This value is not statistically different from that of the control batch.

Fig. 4: Effects of different treatments on sodium levels.

Values are presented as the mean \pm S.E.M. ($n = 6$). ### indicates $p < 0.01$ in comparison with the control group (Group I). ** indicates ($P < 0.01$) comparison with the gentamicin-treated group (Group II). Ts: *Terminalia superba*; GM: gentamicin.

Effects of different treatments on potassium levels

Fig. 5 indicates the effects of the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* on potassium levels. The potassium level of rats treated with gentamicin suffered a significant decrease compared to those gavaged with distilled water (Group I). In fact, this level, which was 11.8 ± 0.14 meq/L, decreased to reach 11.1 ± 0.10 meq/L in those treated with gentamicin (group II). Ts causes a slight and non-significant increase in potassium levels

lowered by gentamicin. The potassium levels of the groups of rats pretreated with doses of 125, 250 and 500 mg/kg bw of Ts by gavage followed by gentamicin did not increase significantly compared to the group of rats treated only with gentamicin. The values are 11.5 ± 0.16 meq/L, 11.5 ± 0.18 meq/L and 11.6 ± 0.14 meq/L, respectively. The potassium level value of rats gavaged with only the dose of 500 mg/kg bw of Ts also did not vary significantly compared to the control group.

Fig. 5: Effects of different treatments on potassium levels.

Values are presented as the mean \pm S.E.M. ($n = 6$). [#] indicates $p < 0.05$ in comparison with the control group (Group I). Ts: *Terminalia superba*; GM: gentamicin.

Effects of different treatments on chlorine levels

The results of the effects of gentamicin and the doses of the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* on the chlorine level of rats are presented in Fig. 6. The results reveal a significant increase in the chlorine level of the group treated with gentamicin compared to the control group. This rate increased from 63.3 ± 4.97 meq/L to 84.0 ± 7.05 meq/L. This rate increased from 63.3 ± 4.97 meq/L to 84.0 ± 7.05 meq/L. Ts significantly reduces

this high level induced by gentamicin. Indeed, the chlorine level of groups of rats pretreated with doses of 125, 250 and 500 mg/kg bw of Ts by gavage followed by gentamicin decreased significantly compared to the group treated with gentamicin. Rats gavaged with only the dose of 500 mg/kg bw of Ts indicate a level of 62.1 ± 1.88 meq/L which is not statistically different from that of the control group.

Fig. 6: Effects of different treatments (Ts) on the chlorine level.

Values are presented as the mean \pm S.E.M. ($n = 6$). [#] indicates $P < 0.05$ in comparison with the control group (Group I). ^{*} Indicates ($P < 0.05$) comparison with the gentamicin-treated group (Group II). Ts: *Terminalia superba*; GM: gentamicin.

Effects of different treatments on body weight and relative kidney weight of rats

The results of the effects of gentamicin and different doses of aqueous extract of *Terminalia superba* on the body weight of rats are recorded in Table 2. They indicate that the body weight of rats force-fed with distilled water increased by $14.6 \pm 0.84\%$ after the 12 days of experimentation. The body weight of rats in the gentamicin-treated group decreased by $3.31 \pm 1.26\%$.

This reduction is significant when compared to that of the control group (group I). As for rats in groups 3, 4, 5 and 6, body weights increased by 9.49 ± 1.22 respectively; 11.1 ± 0.78 ; 7.07 ± 1.46 and $8.88 \pm 1.02\%$. This increase is very significant compared to rats having received only gentamicin. The variation in weight of the rats in the 250 mg/kg bw batch is greater than that of the animals in the 125 and 500 mg/kg bw batches.

Table 2: Effects of the different treatments on the variation in body weight of rats.

Experimental groups	Before treatment	After treatment	Change in body weight (%)	Relative kidney weight (%)
Distilled water	114 ± 5.77	133 ± 4.59	14.6 ± 0.84	0.68 ± 0.03
GM (150 mg/kg)	108 ± 9.19	105 ± 9.05	-3.31 ± 1.26 ^{***}	0.95 ± 0.03 ^{###}
Ts (125 mg/kg) + GM	123 ± 14.2	134 ± 6.71	9.49 ± 1.22 ^{###}	0.87 ± 0.01
Ts (250 mg/kg) + GM	102 ± 8.21	114 ± 5.26	11.1 ± 0.78 ^{###}	0.93 ± 0.02
Ts (500 mg/kg) + GM	103 ± 7.57	111 ± 8.14	7.07 ± 1.46 ^{###}	0.89 ± 0.06
Ts (500 mg/kg)	107 ± 9.90	116 ± 4.85	8.88 ± 1.02 [*]	0.76 ± 0.03

Values are presented as the mean ± S.E.M. (n = 6) * indicates (p < 0.05); and *** indicates (p < 0.001) in comparison with the control group (distilled water). ### indicates p < 0.001 compared to the gentamicin-treated group. Ts: *Terminalia superba*; GM: gentamicin.

Effects of different treatments on relative kidney weight

The results of the effects of gentamicin and the different doses of the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* on the relative weight of the kidneys of the rats are presented in Table 2. The relative weight of the kidneys of the rats from the group treated with gentamicin at a dose of 150 mg/kg bw increases significantly compared to that of the rats from the control group (distilled water). Indeed, the relative weight of the kidneys from the control group is 0.68 ± 0.03% while that of the rats from the group treated with gentamicin is 0.93 ± 0.03%. The relative kidney weights of rats pretreated with Ts doses of 125, 250 and 500 mg/kg bw followed by gentamicin did not vary significantly compared to rats in the gentamicin-treated group. The values obtained are respectively 0.87 ± 0.01%, 0.93 ± 0.02% and 0.89 ± 0.06%. Rats treated only with the dose of 500 mg/kg bw of Ts had a relative weight of 0.76 ± 0.03%. This value is not statistically different from that of the rats in the control group.

DISCUSSION

The results of the biochemical analysis of serum markers of renal damage in samples from the groups of rats revealed, on the one hand, significant increases in creatinine and urea levels in the group of rats treated with gentamicin compared to the control group. Similar results were reported in the work of^[9] who showed a significant increase in the levels of these different markers by gentamicin at a dose of 150 mg/kg bw. On the other hand, a dose-dependent decrease in the levels of these parameters was observed in the groups of rats pretreated with doses of 125, 250 and 500 mg/kg bw of Ts followed by the injection of gentamicin compared to the group treated only with gentamicin. This increase could be due to a failure of the renal system caused by damage to the glomerulus by the action of gentamicin. Indeed, according to,^[10] gentamicin modifies the glomerular filtration rate, the contraction of mesangial cells and the reduction in filtration of the glomerular barrier is due to the neutralization of its negative charges, the proliferation of mesangial cells and apoptosis. This promotes an increase in the level of these markers in the serum. Their concentration in the blood indicates damage at the glomerular level. Therefore, the significant decrease in creatinine and urea levels recorded in the

groups of rats pretreated with Ts would imply the protection of the kidneys against gentamicin-induced renal damage. Similar results were found by^[11] and^[12] These authors showed the nephroprotective potential of *Portulaca oleracea* (Portulacaceae) at doses of 200 and 600 mg/kg bw and of *Myrmecodia pendans* (Rubiaceae) at a dose 250 mg/kg bw. The extracts of these plants considerably reduce the creatinine and urea levels increased by gentamicin. According to,^[13] phytochemical sorting of *Terminalia superba* revealed the presence of polyphenols, flavonoids and tannins. In addition, the antioxidant activity of *T. superba* has been proven by the same authors. Thus, the possible mechanism of kidney protection by Ts could be attributed to its antioxidant power due to its ability to capture free radicals produced in large quantities under the influence of gentamicin.^[9] According to,^[14] measuring serum concentrations of the electrolytes like sodium (Na⁺), potassium (K⁺) and chlorine (Cl⁻) can be used as biomarkers to determine the status of kidney function. The results of the dosages of these ions in blood samples from different batches of rats revealed a significant increase in sodium and chlorine levels, and a decrease in potassium levels in rats treated only with gentamicin. Similar results of the effects of gentamicin on these serum ionic concentrations were obtained in mice in the studies of^[15] These authors showed that gentamicin at a dose of 135 mg/kg bw produces significant nephrotoxicity as well as an increase in sodium and chlorine levels. Other authors who induced gentamicin nephrotoxicity in rats observed that serum electrolyte concentrations of sodium and chlorine increased to 154.2 and 102.25 mmol/L, respectively, after injection of 80 mg/kg bw of gentamicin. In rats treated with aqueous extract of *Thymelaea microphylla* (Thymelaeaceae) at doses of 400 mg/kg bw before gentamicin injection, serum sodium and chlorine levels decreased to 143.5 and 94.6 mmol/L, respectively. At the same time, serum potassium concentrations decreased to 2.6 mmol/L in rats treated only with gentamicin and increased to 3.11 mmol/L in rats previously treated with the aqueous extract of *Thymelaea microphylla* before the injection of 80 mg/kg bw.^[16] The hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* at doses of 250 and 500 mg/kg bw significantly reduced the high sodium and chlorine levels and caused a non-significant increase in the serum potassium level in pretreated animals. This suggests that Ts could be involved in maintaining the balance of these

ions. The decrease in body mass of rats treated with gentamicin would be due to the reduction in their food consumption caused by gentamicin. Ts would therefore inhibit the action of gentamicin by promoting greater food consumption by the rats, and consequently the regain of their weight. Ts could also act on the nerve centers that control feeding behavior to stimulate their activity. These results are in agreement with those of^[17] and^[18] Indeed, according to these authors, the significant and progressive losses in weight of rats treated with gentamicin are remarkable. According to their work, the administration of the aqueous extract of the bark of the trunk of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* (Lauraceae) and the aerial part of *Thymelaea microphylla* (Thymelaeaceae) at doses of 100 and 200 mg/kg bw prevented weight loss induced by gentamicin. The relative kidney weights of rats treated with gentamicin increased significantly compared to those in the distilled water-treated group. Gentamicin was found to be a factor in increasing the kidney weight of animals according to work carried out by^[17] and^[18] Indeed, these showed that the nephrotoxicity induced by gentamicin at doses of 100 and 80 mg/kg bw is the basis of the significant increase in kidney weight. Furthermore, aqueous extracts of *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* (Lauraceae) and *Thymelaea microphylla* (Thymelaeaceae) caused a significant decrease in the relative kidney weights of rats that received them as pretreatment. The use of different doses of Ts followed by the injection of gentamicin led to a reduction in the relative weight of the kidneys compared to the effect of the injection of gentamicin alone, even if this was not significant.

CONCLUSION

The present study was conducted to evaluate the protective effect of the hydro-ethanolic extract of the trunk bark of *Terminalia superba* (Ts) on nephrotoxicity induced by the injection of gentamicin in rats. The administration of gentamicin at 150 mg/kg bw induced disturbances in certain biochemical parameters, significant reductions in body mass and a significant increase in the relative weight of the kidneys in rats. However, when the injection of gentamicin was preceded by oral administration of the hydro-ethanolic extract of *Terminalia superba* at doses of 125; 250 and 500 mg/kg of body weight, these various disturbances caused by gentamicin normalized. The hydro-ethanolic extract of the trunk bark of *Terminalia superba* therefore has a protective effect on the kidneys in rats made nephrotoxic by gentamicin.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare there are no conflicts interests.

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